

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING TABLET OF METOPROLOL SUCCINATE USING COMBINATION OF POLYMERS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 08/05/2020

Available online

30/06/2020

Keywords

Metoprolol Succinate,
HPMC,
Guar Gum,
Xanthan Gum,
Direct Compression,
Wet Granulation.

ABSTRACT

The research was aimed to formulate and evaluate floating tablets of Metoprolol Succinate using a combination of natural polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum as well as a combination of natural and synthetic polymer such as guar gum and HPMC by direct compression and wet granulation method. Metoprolol succinate is a β_1 -selective adrenergic blocker, used in the management of hypertension, angina pectoris etc. Since the drug has relatively short half-life about 3-7hrs, multiple administration is required every 3-7hrs. The addition of gel-forming polymer, and gas-generating agent was essential to achieve buoyancy. Pre-compression parameters like angle of repose, flow rate, bulk density, tapped density, carr's index and hausner's ratio of all formulations showed good flow properties. The four batches of floating tablets were formulated with different polymers and were evaluated for hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content uniformity, Invitro buoyancy, swelling Index, Invitro drug release, adhesion retention period. The formulations containing natural polymers have better-sustained release. It releases the drug upto 12hrs and also shows good buoyancy. The formulation containing (Guar gum + Xanthan gum) prepared by wet granulation method was found to be best among all the formulation batches. It shows floating lag time (20sec) and prolonged floating duration upto (12 hrs) which was controlled release characteristic. The maximum release observed at 11 hrs was 98.88%. The result indicate that floating tablet of Metoprolol Succinate containing Guar gum and Xanthun gum prepared by wet granulation method provide better option for controlled release and improve bioavailability.

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Please cite this article in press as **Namrata R. Singh et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Floating Tablet of Metoprolol Succinate Using Combination of Polymers. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2020:10(06).**

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of the present work was to formulate and evaluate the gastro retentive drug delivery system (Floating matrix tablet) of Metoprolol Succinate using combination of polymers in order to increase their retention in stomach, which ultimately results in the increase of bioavailability along with extended duration of action resulting in possible reduction in dose, less side effects, low overall cost of therapy and hence better patient compliance. The current research was aimed to formulate, evaluate and optimize gastro retentive formulations of Metoprolol Succinate using a combination of natural polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum as well as a combination of natural and synthetic polymer such as guar gum and HPMC by direct compression and wet granulation method (using alcohol).

Metoprolol succinate is a β_1 - selective adrenergic receptor blocking agent used in the management of hypertension, angina pectoris, cardiac arrhythmias, myocardial infarction, heart failure, hyperthyroidism and in the prophylactic treatment of migraine. Since the drug has relatively short half-life about 3-7hrs, in the normal course of therapy multiple administration is required every 3-7hrs. The effervescent-based floating drug delivery was a promising approach to achieve buoyancy.

Metoprolol Succinate, which is better absorbed from the upper part of GIT and have repeated frequency of administration is the best candidates for preparing stomach specific formulations. Gastro retentive formulation of Metoprolol Succinate would increase the residence time of the drug in the stomach with sustained release pattern. This is particularly beneficial in enhancing the therapeutic effect with reduced side effects of drug. The sustained release of the drug is beneficial for decreasing the dosing frequency of the drug, which would lead to the increased patient compliance. Such formulations can be developed at the industrial level to get the maximum benefit and efficient treatment of hypertension, angina pectoris and heart failure.

For solid dosage forms, among all routes of administration, the oral route is most preferable route of administration. Tablets are the most commonly used solid dosage form, administered orally. Oral sustained drug delivery may be complicated because of limited gastric residence time. Rapid gastrointestinal transit can reduce the entire drug release and minimize the effectiveness of given dose because most of the drugs are absorbed within the stomach or the upper part of small intestine[1].

Conventional drug delivery system achieves as well as maintains the drug concentration within the therapeutically effective range only when taken several times a day depending upon the dosage regimen. This result shows significant fluctuation in drug level. An approach overcome such fluctuations conventional led to the development of several novel drug delivery systems (NDDS) that could revolutionize methods of formulation and provide a number of therapeutic benefits.

The main objectives of these new drug delivery systems are :

1) It would be single dose which releases the active ingredient over an extended period of time.

2) It should deliver the active entity directly to the site of action thus minimizing or eliminating the side effects[2].

Controlled release, however, denotes that the system is able to provide some actual therapeutic control, whether this is of a temporal / spatial nature or both. By this the system attempts to control drug concentrations in target tissues for a controlled period of time.

Sustained release dosage forms are designed to release a drug at a predetermined rate by maintaining a constant drug level for a specific period of time with minimum side effects[3].

Dosage forms that can be retained in the stomach are called as gastro retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS)[4]. Gastroretentive dosage form can remain in the gastric region for several hours and hence significantly prolong the gastric residence time of drugs. Prolonged gastric retention improves bioavailability, reduces drug waste and improves solubility of drugs that are less soluble in a high pH environment. It is also suitable for local drug delivery to the stomach and proximal small intestine[5].

A number of systems have been applied to increase the GRT of dosage forms by employing a variety of concepts. but amongst all the systems, Gastro retentive floating drug delivery systems are most commonly used.

Gastro retentive floating drug delivery systems (GRFDDS) have a bulk density lower than that of gastric fluid and thus they remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time. While the system is floating on gastric contents, the drug is slowly released from the system at a desired rate [6]. After complete release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. This results in an increased GRT and a better control of the desired plasma drug concentration[7].

Floating drug delivery system (FDDS) exerts buoyancy in the stomach for an extended period thereby offering extended gastric residence time for the dosage form ensuring optimal bioavailability (BA). The ideal drug candidate for FDDS is drugs that act locally in the upper gastrointestinal tract (GIT) or drugs that get degraded in lower GIT or drugs that show poor absorption in intestine or drugs that are absorbed only in the initial part of the small intestine (SI). Other drugs that are causing gastric lesions or acid-labile drugs are unsuitable for such formulations. The gastric residence time of the dosage form depends upon various factors like size of the dosage form, PH, food intake, and biological factors like age, gender, body mass index, posture, and diseased states (hepatic failure, diabetes, Crohn's disease). Other techniques for gastro retentive dosage forms include swelling or expansion, mucoadhesion, sedimentation, micro balloons and low-density systems, co-administration with drugs that are delaying gastric emptying. Out of all the available systems, the floating beads, floating granules, floating tablets, and floating microspheres have gained major importance in the formulation development more recently[7,8].

The need for gastroretentive dosage forms (GRDFs)

Has led to extensive efforts in both industry and academia towards the formulation of these drug delivery systems. Increasing the gastric residence of a dosage form may be of therapeutic value. Amongst the all methods available, floating dosage forms show considerable promise[8]. The basic idea behind the formulation of such a system is to maintain a desired level of drug in the blood plasma for longer period of time in spite of the fact that the drug does not undergo disintegration. The dosage form usually keeps floating in the gastric fluid and slowly releases the drug at a predetermined rate and maintains desired drug levels in the blood plasma[9]. FDDS has a density less than the gastric fluid and thus they remain buoyant in the stomach for a prolonged period of time without affecting the gastric emptying rate[10]. Prolonged gastric retention enhances bioavailability, minimizes drug waste, and increase solubility of drugs that are less soluble in a high pH environment. Effervescent floating dosage forms prepared by the use of swellable polymers like methylcellulose and various effervescent compounds like sodium bicarbonate, citric acid and tartaric acid. Effervescent floating tablets when comes in contact with the acidic environment of gastric contents, CO₂ is liberated and gets entrapped in swollen polymers, which provides buoyancy to the dosage forms for longer period of time[11]. The objective of present work was to develop gastro retentive formulation using HPMC, guar gum and xanthan gum as a polymer which releases drug in the stomach and upper gastrointestinal (GI) tract, and results in enhanced absorption in the stomach and upper GI tract rather than the lower portions of the GI tract[12].

Metoprolol Succinate is beta selected adrenoreceptor blocking agent, given orally in the treatment of hypertension, angina pectoris and heart failure. It is mainly absorbed from the upper parts of GIT and have good stability in the acidic environment of stomach. Hence it is suitable candidate to formulate in a Floating Drug Delivery System. Metoprolol succinate belongs to class I category in BCS classification system freely soluble & highly permeable. Because of good solubility and permeability, its bioavailability is more and half life is less. It has a half-life of 3 to 7 hours. It is necessary to make repetitive dosing because it may cause nocturnal attack if dose is missed, so objective was to develop the sustained drug delivery system of Metoprolol Succinate that remains for longer time in acidic environment of stomach i.e., floating dosage form which improves the bioavailability[13].

Iupac name : ((+)-1-(isopropyl amino)-3-[p-(2-methoxyethyl)]-2-propanol succinate)

Figure 1:- Structure and Iupac of Metoprolol Succinate.

The drug is freely soluble in water and hence release retarding excipients selection is necessary to achieve a desired in vivo input rate of the drug. The most preferable method of controlling the drug release is to include it in a matrix system. To obtain a desirable drug release profile, cost effectiveness, and broad regulatory acceptance, the Hydrophilic polymer matrix systems are widely used in oral controlled drug delivery. The controlled release system is developed to maintain desired drug concentration in the blood or at target tissues for longer period of time. Hence they can exert a control on the rate of drug release and duration[1,4].

Metoprolol Succinate, which is better absorbed from the upper part of GIT and have repeated frequency of administration is the best candidates for preparing stomach specific formulations. Gastro retentive formulation of Metoprolol Succinate would increase the residence time of the drug in the stomach with sustained release pattern. This is particularly beneficial in enhancing the therapeutic effect with reduced side effects of drug. The sustained release of the drug is beneficial for decreasing the dosing frequency of the drug, which would lead to the increased patient compliance. Such formulations can be developed at the industrial level to get the maximum benefit and efficient treatment of hypertension, angina pectoris and heart failure.

This research project was undertaken to prepare GRDF of Metoprolol Succinate for increasing their retention in upper GIT.

Following are the objectives of the present research work:

1. To carry out the preliminary studies for selection of excipients and for preparing the floating matrix tablet of Metoprolol Succinate.
2. To carry out the drug excipient compatibility studies
3. To perform the preformulation study of Metoprolol Succinate.
4. To identify the key variable affecting the formulation of gastro retentive floating matrix tablet.
5. To apply an appropriate statistical design for the optimization of the floating matrix tablets.
6. To prepare and optimize the floating matrix tablets by suitable method.
7. To evaluate the prepared floating matrix tablets.
8. To analyse the data observed during evaluation of floating tablets.
9. Results and conclusion

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material

Metoprolol succinate received as gift sample from 'Rubicon pharmaceutical company', Thane. All the excipients such as HPMC K4M, Guar gum, Xanthan gum, MCC, Sodium bicarbonate, Citric acid, PVP, Lactose, Magnesium stearate, talc and isopropyl alcohol were obtained on lab scale from Ideal College of Pharmacy and Research, Kalyan. All reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade satisfying pharmacopeial standards.

Methodology

Preparation of gastro retentive floating tablets

Floating tablets were prepared by two different methods. By direct compression and wet granulation technique using variable concentrations of HPMC-K4M, Guar gum, Xanthan gum.

Direct Compression Method

Different tablets formulations were prepared by the direct compression technique. All the powders were passed through 100 mesh sieve. The required quantity of drug, polymers, sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, MCC, lactose, PVP, magnesium stearate, talc were mixed thoroughly. Mixing was continued for another minute and the mixed blend was studied for precompression parameters. Finally, required quantity of mixture was weighed and then compressed using a tablet compression machine.

Wet Granulation Method

All the powders were passed through 100 mesh sieve. The required quantity of drug and polymers were mixed thoroughly. The wet mass is formed by mixing all ingredients with PVP in alcohol. The wet mass is then passed through 12 mesh sieve. Granules are then collected and dried in oven. After granules are completely dried they were again passed through 20 mesh sieve placed above and below this 40 mesh sieve is placed. Granules are retained on 40 mesh sieve and fine is collected and 10% fine added to granules. Talc and magnesium stearate were finally added as glidant and lubricant respectively. Mixing was continued for another minute and the mixed blend was studied for precompression parameters. Finally, required quantity of mixture was weighed. The granules are then compressed using a tablet compression machine. Each tablet contained 100mg of Metoprolol succinate and other pharmaceutical ingredients as listed in table no 1 in each section.

Table no 1:- Composition of Each tablet Ingredients.

Ingredients	MF1	MF2	MF3	MF4
	(Wet Granulation)	(Direct Compression)	(Wet Granulation)	(Direct Compression)
Metoprolol Succinate	100	100	100	100
HPMC K4M	100	100	-	-
Guar Gum	100	100	100	100
Xanthan Gum	-	-	100	100
Sodium bicarbonate	20	20	20	20
Citric acid	10	10	10	10
MCC	5	5	5	5
Lactose	4	4	4	4
PVP	5	5	5	5
Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3	3
Talc	3	3	3	3
Isopropyl alcohol	-	-	q.s.	q.s.
TOTAL :	350	350	350	350

Development of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Metoprolol Succinate

UV spectrophotometric method for estimation of Metoprolol Succinate in 0.1N HCL is used for estimation of MS in tablet dosage form, already established assay method was used.

Calibration Curve of MS in 0.1 N HCl as a Solvent

The calibration curve of MS in 0.1 N HCl was used for determination of drug release during *in vitro* release measurements.

Preparation of stock solution

Accurately weighed 100 mg of MS was transferred in 100 ml volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved and diluted upto the mark with 0.1 N HCl to give a solution with concentration of 1000 µg/ml. An aliquot of 10 ml from the above solution was withdrawn and diluted upto 100 ml with 0.1 N HCl to obtain a stock solution having concentration of 100µg/ml.

Preparation of solutions to obtain calibration curve

Appropriate aliquots from stock solution of MS (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 and 1 ml) were accurately withdrawn in 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with 0.1 N HCl to obtain the final concentration of solution in range of 1-10 µg/ml. For spectroscopic measurement drug free solvent was used as a blank. To measure the λ_{max} , solution of 10 µg/ml was scanned in the range of 200-400nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer. Absorbance of prepared solutions of calibration plot was measured at λ_{max} of MS. The procedure for measurement of absorbance was performed in triplicate. Value of the absorbance was plotted against concentration to obtain a calibration curve.

Viscosity of Polymers

Polymeric solutions of 1% (w/v) concentration of all the polymers were prepared in 100ml of water. The viscosities of the prepared Polymeric solutions were determined by using Brookfield viscometer, suitable RPM and spindle were selected and viscosity was determined[19].

Pre Compression Parameters

Drug-Excipient Compatibility studies

Drug is an active part of dosages form and it is mainly responsible for therapeutic value and Excipient substances which are included along with drugs being formulated in a dosage form so as to impart specific qualities to them. It is important for determination of Stability of the dosage forms. It is also used for development of new drug delivery system as well a investigation of new drug product. Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer or DSC. Because of unavailability of IR and DSC we have used the minor method i.e. TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography) for estimation of drug-excipient compatibility.[20]

Procedure

The Equal portion of Drug and Excipient (1:1 ratio) is added in Ampules and the Ampules are placed in Stability Chamber at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one Week, After One Week the Drug Excipient Compatibility Study is determined by using TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography) (In TLC mobile phase is methanol: water: glacial acetic acid).

Evaluation of granules

Angle of repose, Flow rate, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's (compressibility) index and Hausner's ratio are determined to find out the flow property of granules during formulation.[13]

Angle of repose

The Angle of repose was determined, in order to determine the flow property. It is defined as 'The maximum angle that can be obtained between the free standing surface of the powder heap and the horizontal plane.'

$$\Theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where,

h = height

r = radius

Θ = angle of repose

Procedure:

- An accurately weighed sample was taken.
- A funnel was fixed in the stand in such a way that the tip of the funnel was at the height of 2.5cm from the surface.
- The sample was passed through the funnel slowly to form a heap.
- The height and the circumference of the powder heap formed were measured.
- The radius was measured and the angle of repose was determined using the above formula.

Flow rate

It is defined as the 'Mass of the powder / granules passing through a given surface per unit time'. It is represented by (gm/sec).

$$\text{Flow rate} = \frac{\text{Mass of powder / granules (gm)}}{\text{Time for flow (sec)}}$$

Compressibility index (Carr's indices)

Compressibility is the ability of powder under pressure. It is an indication of the compressibility of a powder. Compressibility index is an important measure that can be obtained from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. A material having values of less than 20 to 30% is defined as the free flowing material.

$$\% \text{Compressibility} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density} \times 100}{\text{Tapped density}}$$

Bulk density

The bulk density is the ratio of the mass of an untapped powder/ granules sample and its volume including the contribution of the interparticulate void volume. Hence, the bulk density depends on both the density of powder particles and the spatial arrangement of particles in the powder bed. The bulk density is expressed in grams per ml (g/ml).

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Mass of powder/granules (gm)}}{\text{Volume of powder/granules before tapping (ml)}}$$

Procedure

- A quantity of 5g of the powder from each formula was introduced into a 25 ml measuring cylinder.
- The initial volume from measuring cylinder was observed.

Tapped density

The tapped density is the ratio of the mass of the powder to the volume occupied by the powder/ granules after it has been tapped for a defined period of time. The tapped density is an increased bulk density attained after mechanically tapping a container containing the powder/granules sample. Tapped density is obtained by mechanically tapping a graduated measuring cylinder.

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Mass of powder/ granules (gm)}}{\text{Volume of powder/granules after tapping (ml)}}$$

Procedure:

- After observing the initial powder volume or weight, the measuring cylinder or vessel is mechanically tapped.
- Again volume or weight readings are taken until little further volume or weight change is observed.

Hausner's ratio

The Hausner ratio is a number that is correlated to the flowability of a powder or granular material. A Hausner ratio greater than 1.25 is considered to be an indication of poor flowability.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Post Compression Parameters[13]**Thickness**

The thickness of the tablets was determined by using vernier calipers. Five tablets were used, and average values were calculated.

Hardness

Hardness indicates the ability of a tablet to withstand mechanical shocks while handling. The hardness of the tablets was determined using Pfizer hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm². Three tablets were randomly picked and hardness of the tablets was determined.

Weight variation test

To study weight variation twenty tablets of the formulation were weighed using an electronic balance and the test was performed according to the official method. Twenty tablets were selected randomly from each batch and weighed individually to check for weight variation. Percent weight variation was calculated by using the following equation.

$$\% \text{ Weight Variation} = \frac{\text{Average Weight} - \text{Individual Weight} \times 100}{\text{Average Weight}}$$

Friability Test

Friability testing is used to test the durability of tablets during packing processes and transit. This involves repeatedly dropping a sample of tablets over a fixed time, using a rotating drum with a baffle. The result is inspected for broken tablets, and the percentage of tablet mass lost through chipping. The friability of tablets was determined using Roche friabilator. It is expressed in percentage (%).

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{W_{\text{initial}} - W_{\text{final}} \times 100}{W_{\text{initial}}}$$

% Friability of tablets less than 1% are considered acceptable.

Procedure:

- Ten tablets were initially weighed (W_{initial}) and transferred into friabilator.
- The friabilator was operated at 25rpm for 4 minutes or run up to 100 revolutions.
- The tablets were removed and weighed (W_{final}) again.

The % friability was then calculated.

Drug content uniformity (Assay)

10tablets of each formulation were weighed and taken in a mortar and crushed to powder. A quantity of powder equivalent to 100mg of Metoprolol Succinate was accurately weighed and transferred to a 100ml volumetric flask and 0.1N HCL solution was added and mixed thoroughly. The solution was made up to volume 100ml and filtered. Dilute 1ml of the resulting solution to 10ml with 0.1N HCL solution. The absorbance of resulting solution was measured at 274nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The linearity equation obtained from calibration curve was used for estimation of Metoprolol Succinate in the tablet formulations.

In vitro buoyancy studies

The in vitro buoyancy was determined by floating lag time method described. The tablets were placed in 250 ml beaker containing 0.1 N HCl. The time required for the tablets to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating lag time. The time between introduction of dosage form and its buoyancy in 0.1 N HCl and the time during which the dosage form remain buoyant were measured.[13]

Floating Lag Time (FLT) or Buoyancy Lag Time (BLT) : The time taken for dosage form to emerge on surface of medium.

Total Floating Time (TFT) : Total duration of time by which dosage form remain buoyant.

In Vitro dissolution studies

The release rate of Metoprolol Succinate from floating tablets was determined using The United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) XXIV dissolution testing apparatus II (paddle method). The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl, at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 75 rpm. A sample (5 ml) of the solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus hourly for 8 hours, and the samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The samples diluted to a suitable concentration with 0.1N HCl. Absorbance of these solutions was measured at 222 nm using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated using the equation obtained from a standard curve.[13]

Swelling Index or Water Uptake Test

The swelling properties of matrices containing drug were determined by placing the tablet in the dissolution test apparatus containing 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl and maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. After 12hrs, the tablets were taken out of the medium and the weight gain in each tablet was checked using electronic weighing balance. The swelling index was expressed in terms of the percentage water uptake (WU %) according to the equation. [1].

$$\text{WU} = \frac{\text{Weight of the swollen tablet} - \text{Initial weight of the tablet}}{\text{Initial weight of the tablet}} \times 100$$

Adhesion Retention Period

The adhesion retention period of the tablets was evaluated, in triplicate, by an in vitro method. Briefly, an agar plate (2%, w/w) was prepared in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2). A side of the tablet was wetted with 0.1 N HCl and attached to the centre of agar plate by applying a light force with a fingertip. Five minutes later, the agar plate was attached to a USP disintegration test apparatus and moved up and down in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The tablet adhered on the plate was immersed into the solution at the lowest point and got out of the solution at the highest point. The retention period of the tablet on the plate was noted visually.[21].

Figure 2:- In vitro adhesion study of MS floating matrix tablets, in USP disintegration test apparatus.

Stability studies

The optimized formulation of Metoprolol Succinate were packed in amber color bottle and aluminum foil laminated on the upper part of the bottle and these packed formulation was stored in stability chamber maintained at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ RH for 1 month. The samples were withdrawn periodically and evaluated for their drug content, in vitro buoyancy studies and for in vitro drug release.[22,23]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification of Drugs

Identification of Drug by Description, Solubility and Melting Point

An identification of Metoprolol Succinate based on physical examination and melting point results are mentioned in following table.

Table no 2:- Identification of drug by Description, Solubility and Melting Point.

Sr. No.	Test	Specification	Observation	Inference
1	State	Solid crystalline	Solid crystalline	Complies
2	Color	White	White	Complies
3	Taste	Bitter	Not Performed	Complies
4	Melting Point	120°C	121°C	Complies
5	Solubility	Freely soluble in water, soluble in methanol and Sparingly soluble in ethanol	Freely soluble in water, Soluble in methanol and Sparingly soluble in ethanol	Complies

Analytical method

Development of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of MS:

Table no 3:-Absorbance values for given Concentration by UV spectrophotometric Method.

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
1	0.0423
2	0.0871
3	0.1261
4	0.1677
5	0.2002
6	0.2345
7	0.291
8	0.3307
9	0.3692
10	0.4121

Figure 3:- Standard Calibration Curve of MS at 274nm in 0.1N HCL.

The calibration curve of Metoprolol Succinate is obtained in 0.1 N HCl and it was used for determination of drug release during *in vitro* release measurements.

Slope = 0.040 and $R^2 = 0.998$.

Viscosity of Polymers

Polymeric solutions of 1% (w/v) concentration of all the polymers were prepared and the viscosities of the prepared Polymeric solutions are as follows;

Table no 4:- Viscosity value of Polymers obtained from Brookfield Viscometer.

Polymer	HPMC K4M	Guar gum	Xanthan gum
Viscosity in (cp)	15	537	562

Pre Compression Parameters

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies

The Drug and Excipient Compatibility studies determined by TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography) Method In which The TLC of Drug, Drug and Excipient before Stability Chamber and After Stability Chamber is reported in Table no.5.

Table no 5:- Retention Factor of samples by TLC method.

Sr No.	Samples	Retention Factor of drug Before the Stability Chamber	Retention Factor of drug After the Stability Chamber
1	Pure Drug (Metoprolol Succinate)	0.45	0.48
2	Metoprolol Succinate + HPMC K4M	0.40	0.42
3	Metoprolol Succinate + Guar Gum	0.38	0.41
4	Metoprolol Succinate + Xanthan Gum	0.48	0.45

Evaluation of granules

Table no 6:- Values for evaluation of granules for pre compression analysis.

Batch Code	Angle of Repose (Θ) ($^\circ$)	Flow Rate (gm/sec)	Compressibility Index (%)	Bulk Density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped Density (gm/cm ³)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	29.03	0.58	12.6	0.416	0.476	1.14
F2	26.24	0.66	12.6	0.416	0.476	1.14
F3	26.24	0.83	8.82	0.434	0.476	1.09
F4	24.84	0.76	8.82	0.434	0.476	1.09

Post Compression Parameters

Table no 7:- Values for post compression analysis of Tablet.

Batch Code	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Weight Variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug Content (%)
F1	3.85	2.2	351.90	0.617	94.93
F2	3.90	1.8	352.83	0.407	101.22
F3	3.82	2.4	349.78	0.317	99.56
F4	3.92	2.3	352.45	0.412	98.33

All the formulation showed values within the prescribed limits for tests like Friability, Weight variation, Drug content which indicates that the prepared tablets are of standard quality within official ranges.

In Vitro dissolution studies

In vitro drug release study of Metoprolol Succinate Floating tablet was carried out by using 0.1N HCl at temperature $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with at 75 rpm for 12hrs. In vitro dissolution data was subjected to graphical treatment i.e. percentage drug release Vs time.

Table no 8:- In vitro drug release [%] tested by Dissolution apparatus.

	F1	F2	F3	F4
Time [hrs]	Cumulative drug release [%]			
1	9.47	8.055	7.92	7.2
2	22.56	17.64	16.425	13.7
3	34.76	28.03	25.177	21.75
4	42.68	38.83	34.29	30.57
5	53.37	50.53	43.58	39.28
6	65.25	58.34	53.43	48.3
7	78.34	70.62	62.14	59.22
8	90.22	83.79	71.41	71.86
9	103.65	94.92	80.97	83.67
10	110.85	107.57	90.83	91.8
11	119.56	119.45	98.88	97.47
12	130.41	130.09	104.69	106.92

All the Four formulation of prepared floating tablets of Metoprolol succinate were subjected to in vitro release studies. The release data obtained for formulations F1 to F4 were shows the plot of cumulative % drug released as a function of time for different formulations. The in vitro release of all four batches of floating tablets showed the release with an initial effect. In the first hour % drug released were 9.47, 8.05, 7.92 and 7.2 for F1, F2, F3 and F4 respectively. From the in-vitro dissolution data it was found that F1, F2, F3 and F4 released more than 60% of drug within 8 hr. It concludes that F3 and F4 formulation releases the drug upto 12hrs. Hence F3 and F4 had better controlled release than the other formulation.

Figure 4:- Graph for In vitro drug release of MS in USP dissolution testing apparatus II.

In vitro buoyancy studies (Determination of Floating Properties) :

The tablets were evaluated for Floating lag time and Duration of floating time.

Table no 9:- Floating Properties of batch F1 to F4

Batch Code	Buoyancy Lag Time	Total Floating Time
F1	20min	Upto 12hrs
F2	40sec	Upto 12hrs
F3	20sec	Upto 12hrs
F4	30sec	Upto 12hrs

On immersion in 0.1N HCl solution pH (1.2) at 37°C, the tablets floated, and remained buoyant without disintegration. The floating time was determined and result obtained shows that batch F1 to F4 float for 12 hours. The buoyancy lag time was obtained in the range of 20 to 40 seconds for F2 to F3 and for F1, it was 20min. Among all the batches the (F3) formulation shows best buoyancy lag time and floating duration. And F1 shows poor buoyancy lag time as compared to F2, F3 and F4. From the results it can be concluded that the batch containing natural polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum showed good Buoyancy lag time (BLT) and Total floating time (TFT).

Figure 5(a):- Floating of tablet at 50sec.

Figure 5(b):- Floating of tablet at 20min.

Figure 5(c):- Floating of tablet at 6hrs.

Figure 5(d):- Floating of tablet after 12hrs.

Swelling Index or Water Uptake Test

The %swelling index of all formulations after 12hrs were found to be in range of 74.28 to 105.71, as shown in table. Amongst all formulation F3 exhibited highest swelling index. This formulation was found to be intact for 8hrs and deformed after 24hrs, showing that the formulation would eventually go out of the stomach after the release of the drug, which is desirable. Minimum swelling index was found for the formulation F1 which means that the polymer doesn't promote water uptake by polymeric matrices containing HPMC.

Table no 10:- Swelling Index of MS Floating Tablet.

Batch code	F1	F2	F3	F4
Swelling index (%)	74.28	94.28	105.71	97.14

Figure 6:- Swollen Tablets after 12hrs.

Adhesion Retention Period

Agar plates were used to check the comparative adhesion retention of the prepared formulations as it has negatively charged ions, alike mucin covering the mucous membrane. Agar gel contains large numbers of negative charges because of the presence of carboxyl and sulfate groups present in it.

Table no 11:- Adhesion retention period (min) of MS Floating tablet.

Batch code	F1	F2	F3	F4
Tablet adhesion retention period (min)	40.15	52.30	95.50	67.15

The formulations gave the tablet retention between the ranges of 40 to 96 minutes, as shown in table. On performing the comparative adhesion retention period study for prepared tablets, it was found that tablets prepared with Guar gum and Xanthan gum by wet granulation method gave maximum adhesion retention of 95.50 minutes and formulation prepared using HPMC K4M and Guar gum exhibited minimum adhesion retention period. Formulation with Xanthan gum was retained on the agar plate for a longer period of time as compared to other formulations.

Stability Studies

The results of stability studies did not show any significant change in the physical appearance, drug content, in vitro buoyancy studies, and in vitro dissolution studies of above four formulations as shown in Table.

Table no 12:- Evaluation of tablet after 1month for Stability study.

Formulation	Drug Content	Floating Behaviour		In vitro drug release at 12 th hr
		FLT	TFT	
F1	94.50	22min	Upto 12hrs	104
F2	98.30	30sec	Upto 12hrs	110
F3	105.80	25sec	Upto 12hrs	99.2
F4	95.20	40sec	Upto 12hrs	95.98

CONCLUSION

This study discusses the preparation of gastroretentive tablets of Metoprolol Succinate using a combination of natural polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum as well as a combination of natural and synthetic polymer such as guar gum and HPMC by direct compression and wet granulation method (using alcohol), that could retain in the stomach for longer periods of time delivering the drug to the site of action, i.e., stomach. The effervescent-based floating drug delivery was a promising approach to achieve in vitro buoyancy. The addition of gel-forming polymer HPMC K4M, natural polymer such as xanthan gum and guar gum, gas-generating agent sodium bicarbonate and citric acid was essential to achieve in vitro buoyancy.

1. The pre-compression parameters of all formulations showed good flow properties and these can be used for tablet manufacture.
2. The post-compression parameters of all formulations were determined and the values were found to be satisfactory.
3. From the drug content and *in-vitro* dissolution studies of the formulations, it was concluded that the formulation F3 i.e. the formulation containing natural polymers i.e. Guar gum and Xanthan gum is the best formulation.
4. Also the formulations prepared by wet granulation method (using alcohol) shows good floating properties as well as better drug release as compared to the formulations prepared by direct compression method.
5. The % Cumulative drug release of all the formulations F1, F2, F3 and F4 was able to sustain the drug release for 12 hrs. F3 and F4 formulations containing natural polymers showed good integrity for 12 hrs.
6. As a result of this study it may be concluded that the floating tablets using a natural polymers like guar gum and xanthan gum in optimized concentration prepared by wet granulation method (using alcohol) can be used to increase the GRT of the dissolution fluid in the stomach to deliver the drug in a controlled manner. The concept of formulating floating tablets of Metoprolol Succinate.

The results of the present research work demonstrates that the combination of both natural and synthetic polymers as well as combination of natural polymers by using direct compression as well as wet granulation method successfully employed for formulating the sustained release matrix tablets of MS. Amongst all, F3 and F4 formulation containing natural polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum shows good release property as well as good buoyancy. And the formulations prepared by wet granulation method (using alcohol) shows good buoyancy and better release. Hence we can conclude that the combination of natural polymers shows better sustain release and buoyancy as compared to combination of synthetic polymer and wet granulation method is more preferable as compared to direct compression method. The formulation (F3) containing (Guar gum + Xanthun gum) was found to be best among all the formulation batches. It's showed floating lag time (20sec) and prolonged floating duration up to (12 hrs) which was controlled release characteristic. The maximum release observed at 11 hrs was 98.88%. The result indicate that floating tablet of Metoprolol Succinate containing Guar gum and Xanthun gum prepared by wet granulation (using alcohol) method provide better option for controlled release and improve bioavailability. As this natural polymer are nontoxic and non-irritant also it does not show any side effects Hence these formulation containing natural polymers can be preferred over the formulation containing synthetic polymers. So, by using various combination of different polymers can be used to formulate floating tablets.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my special thanks of gratitude to my teacher Mr. Sujeet Ubale as well as our principal Mrs. Smita Takarkhede who gave me the golden opportunity to do this wonderful project on the topic 'Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating Tablet Of Metoprolol Succinate Using Combination Of Polymers' which also helped me in doing a lot of Research and I came to know about so many new things I am really thankful to them. Secondly I would also like to thank Mr. Manohar Mirchandani sir, my parents and friends who helped me a lot in finalizing this project within the limited time frame.

ABBREVIATIONS:

C _{max}	: Maximum Plasma Concentration
CR	: Controlled Release
DSC	: Differential Scanning Calorimetry
FT-IR	: Fourier-Transform Infrared
GIT	: Gastrointestinal Tract
GRDDS	: Gastro-Retentive Dosage Forms
GRDF	: Gastroretentive Dosage Forms
GRT	: Gastric Retention Time
HCl	: Hydrochloric Acid
HPMC	: Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose
ICH	: International Conference on Harmonization
MCC	: Microcrystalline Cellulose
MS	: Metoprolol Succinate
PVP	: Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone
QC	: Quality Control
TLC	: Thin Layer Chromatography
USP	: United State Pharmacopoeia

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